

1 **Phospholipase C controls energy in the cell through direct regulation of an mTOR nutrient sensing**
2 **machine and the PI3-kinase.**

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7 We demonstrate here control of energy in the cell by phospholipase C. Heterozygous and homozygous
8 mutation of PLCy2 at S707Y activated energy resources in the cell. PLCy2 S707Y resulted in activation of
9 nutrient sensor *TSC22D1* concomitant with activation. Consistent with a role for TBC family molecules in
10 feedback signaling to balance nutrient (amino acid) utilization within a closed energy system, *TBC1D5* was
11 silenced in cells expressing the phospholipase C mutation PLCy2 S707Y.

12 Citations

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16 polyphosphoinositide-specific phospholipase C activity by purified Gq. *Science*, 251(4995), pp.804-807.